

Challenges in the Training and Education of Library and Information Science Students in Nigeria: A Case Study of Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State

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Abstract

This study investigates the Challenges in the Training and Education of Library and Information Science Students in Nigeria: A Case Study of Niger Delta University. Three specific objectives of the study and three research questions guided the study. Descriptive survey research method was adopted. The population of the study was 45 final year LIS students of the Niger Delta University. The sample size the population of the study, using census sampling technique. The study employed survey questionnaire (CTELISSNCSNDUQ) as instrument for data collection of the study. Frequency count, simple percentages and tabular presentation were the statistical tools used. The findings of this research were: demonstration library and laboratory are not available in the Niger Delta University library school; Lacking information sources and other facilities for teaching and learning; Limitations on how to supply library services & enhance teaching and learning using new digital technologies; Inadequate teaching and learning facilities; Inadequate industrial attachments; Shortage of high ranking teaching staff in Library and Information Science Department; Skills and attitudes of some LIS lecturers; and Poor information environment, were the challenges hindering the smooth training and education of LIS students in NDU, among others. The study recommended that: Review of existing curriculum. It is recommended that there is a need to reorient Library and information Science Education to reflect global changes and evolving market demands; Establishing links and collaborations between Library and Information Science schools and information centers; and There is a need to introduce and maintain interaction and collaboration between Library and Information Science employers and Library and Information Science professionals particularly the educators to create dialogue among stakeholders; among others.

Keywords: Challenges, Training, Education, Library, Information, Science, Students

Introduction

Library and information science (LIS) training and education play a significant role in the production of high quality LIS students who occupy a unique position in national development. LIS students are gatekeepers and brokers of information which is essential for knowledge acquisition, decision-making and national development. The success of library, archives and information centres in effectively meeting their obligation of information provision

is hinged, in part, on the development of skilled manpower.

Trained personnel are a key requirement in library and information work. In this respect, LIS education plays a vital role (Edegbo, 2011). Although early LIS students, particularly librarians did not undergo any formal training (Wikipedia, nd.), the modern day challenges of library and information work require that personnel should be well-trained and educated to

make for effectiveness.

Melvin Dewey, the famous proponent of the Dewey Decimal Classification System was said to have established the first library school in the United States in 1887 at Columbia University (Wikipedia, n.d.). In Europe, the library School established in Barcelona in 1915 is reputed to be the oldest library school in that continent. Many other library schools were said to have been established during the Second World War. In Africa, however, South Africa is credited with the longest history of LIS in the continent dating from 1938 (Ocholla, 2007).

In West Africa, the earliest formal training in librarianship consisted of short courses organized by practicing librarians and these were aimed solely at preparing the participants for the British Library Association examinations which then constituted the only gateway for aspiring librarians (Aguolu and Aguolu, 2002). One of such courses took place in Achimota College, Gold Coast (now Ghana) in 1944 and it drew participants from various West African countries including Nigeria. This appears to be the earliest evidence of the strong historical link between Ghana and Nigeria in the education and training of LIS students. Hence this study tends to study the challenges in the training and education of library and information science students.

The Niger Delta University Library was established in the 2001/2002 academic session. Presently the Niger Delta University Library is housed in a state of the art building and has the capacity to seat two thousand (2,000) students. The library collection stands at ninety-seven thousand five hundred and fifty (97,550.00). In addition to the Main Library the University has College of Health Sciences and nine (9) faculty libraries. The vision of the Library is to “promote excellent information delivery service” while the mission is to “promote a culture of broad inquiry and support the university’s mission through discovery, preservation, and dissemination of knowledge and creative expression for the benefit of the university community and social cultural and economic well-being of mankind”.

Statement of the Problem

Library and information science (LIS) education and training are critical in preparing professionals to meet the evolving needs of the information society. However, there are several challenges that LIS students face in their education and training, which hinder their effective learning and development. These challenges include outdated curricula, inadequate teaching methods, limited access to resources, and insufficient exposure to technological advancements. The problem is that these challenges negatively impact the quality of education and training received by LIS students, which, in turn, affects their preparedness for the workforce and their ability to meet the needs of the industry. Therefore, there is a need to identify and analyze the challenges faced by LIS students in their education and training and explore possible solutions to address them.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the Challenges in the Training and Education of Library and Information Science Students in Nigeria: A Case Study of Niger Delta University. The specific objectives are:

1. To find out whether demonstration libraries and laboratories are available in the Niger Delta University library school.
2. To identify the challenges that hinder the training and education of library and information science students in the Niger Delta University library school.
3. To explore likely solutions to the challenges facing training and education of library and information science students in Niger Delta University.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. Are demonstration libraries and laboratories available in the Niger Delta University library school?

2. What are the challenges that hinder the training and education of library and information science students in the Niger Delta University library school?
3. What are the likely solutions to the challenges facing training and education of library and information science students in NDU?

Review of Related Literature

Demonstration Library and Laboratory in LIS Schools

Demonstration libraries in Nigerian universities are typically small libraries located within academic departments or faculties that serve as teaching and learning resources for students and faculty members. These libraries often house a collection of textbooks, reference materials, and other resources specific to the subject area of the department. Teachers need various kinds of information for teaching and research for the purposes of impacting knowledge in students and self development. To achieve this, the right information must be available for the right person at the right time in its appropriate format (Aina & Adekan, 2013).

The implementation of staff development poses a number of challenges to information professionals in providing effective library services. In developing countries, especially in Nigeria, staff development in special libraries are relegated to the background. According to Onah (2003) the problems of staff development are connected to the inability of the authority in addressing the issue of selecting and releasing staff for training by the organization. He emphasized that in a bureaucracy where merit forms only a part of the system of recruiting and promoting civil servants instead of being the ultimate, the process of selecting staff development is bound to be affected by non-merit criteria. He maintains that in Nigeria, the process has been affected by other criteria such as political, qualification, years of service, gender, ethnicity and favouritism, and the geo-political spread of development opportunities (quota system based). This phenomenon is contrary to

the principles of development by its merit to enhance efficient management in the sense that some staffs selected for staff programmes may not know the job or cope with the tasks of administrative development course. He concluded that apart from problems of funds, the library as an organization as well as special libraries faces lack of good leadership as a problem that is affecting staff development courses.

Yemi-Peters & Oladokun (2023) put forward that Education in library and information science faces a number of difficulties in Nigeria. Many research on various aspects of LIS education have been conducted in Africa, particularly Nigeria. Insufficient teaching resources at LIS training, a lack of adequate ICT content in the courses, insufficient course length, courses that are wholly unrelated to the job market, and a lack of industrial attachments for LIS students are all said to contribute to LIS training programmes not adequately addressing current job market requirements, according to Mohanan and Vijesh (2020). He urged that they assess and revise their plans to take into account the demands of the labour market.

Amunga and Khayesi (2012) claim that there are many obstacles to LIS education, such as a shortage of teaching personnel in LIS schools, outdated curricula, a lack of information resources and other teaching/learning facilities, inadequate financing for LIS schools and departments, low completion rates, and waste. Okello-Obura and Kigongo-Bukenya (2011) claim that LIS education has a number of difficulties, including the fact that most LIS institutions still fall short in terms of quality and standard in order to accommodate the many students who enrol due to the strong demand for higher education.

Challenges Hindering Training and Education in Library and Information Science

Asogwa (2023) noted that Lack of ICT (Information Communication Technology)

Infrastructure constitutes one of the major challenges as Zakari (2000) stated that ensuring that large number of students acquires ICT skills requires that students have access to appropriate hardware's and software's. This often involves installing and maintaining many classroom workstations or networked computers. However, a peep into the library and information science schools show that a good number of them do not have dedicated ICT laboratories as in the case of university of Nigeria Nsukka, Delta State University and so on. In schools where they are available they are inadequate in terms of space and ICT facilities (Jenson, 2005).

In continuation, inadequate funding is equally a challenge facing library schools in Nigeria as Manjanja (2006) noted that library schools in Nigeria are constrained by poor funding for as long as funding does not improve appreciably, the present unsatisfied situation in the library schools are unlikely to change for better. Brain drain is yet another challenge as Odongo (2006) emphasized that staff sent overseas for training either do not return to their post or taken up by other organization that are able to offer higher remuneration.

Strategies For Improving ICT Application To Management Of Library Resources

Strategies are usually the measures, scheme, plan of action, approach, schedule, master plan or blueprint adopted by an organisations, institutions, or individuals in order to carry out any action for the purpose of accomplishing tasks (Vincent, 2011). The developing world is driven by Information Communication Technology (ICTs) and information service providers have been preparing to catch up with the global trend so that they will not be abandoned.

Etim (2006) observed that the strategies to cope with the challenges of Information Communication Technology (ICTs) application in Nigerian information centers must start with education for librarianship. He stressed that the advocacy for continuing professional education becomes inevitable, especially, in core competencies of Information Communication Technology.

Methodology

This study employed the use of survey research design. The choice of this research design was considered appropriate because of its advantages of identifying attributes of a large population from a group of individuals. The population of this study consist of forty-five (45) final year students of the Department of Library and Information Science of the Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island. As a result of the small number in population, the sample size was 45 students, minus the researcher which is equal to 44 using enumeration sampling technique.

Data was collected through questionnaire carefully designed and administered to the respondents. The questionnaire is the major instrument for data collection. The questionnaire contains sections A and B. Section A contains personal information about the respondents. Section B is the main body of the questionnaire. This section contains close ended questions using a two (2) point scale instrument through which the opinions of the respondents were expressed. Their responses will be measured by means of a fixed-category rating system of Yes and No. The questionnaires was administered to the respondents during official hours at the office, by a librarian in charge, who doubles as a research assistant. Tables, frequency counts and simple percentages will be used as statistical technique for analyzing the research questions.

Data Analysis

Demographic Variables

Table 1: Distribution and Return of Questionnaire

No. of Questionnaire Distributed	No. Returned
45	35 (77.7%)

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 1 shows that, of the 45 copies of questionnaire distributed, 35 (77.7%) were successfully retrieved from the respondents and found usable.

Table 2: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	19	54
Female	16	46

TOTAL	35	100
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Source: Field survey, 2024.

From the table above, 19 (54%) respondents were male while 16(46%) were female. This implies that majority of the staff were male.

Table 3: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-20 years	--	--
21-30 years	35	100
31 years and above	--	--
Total	35	100%

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 3 shows that all the respondents of this study fall within 21 -30 age category. This implies that the Library and Information Science final year students (2022/2023 academic session) of the Niger Delta University were very young graduates heading to the labor market.

Test of Research Questions

Research Question 1: Are demonstration libraries and laboratories available in the Niger Delta University library schools?

Table 4: demonstration libraries and laboratories availability

S/n	Statement	Yes (%)	No (%)	Decision
1	NDU library school have electronic library for teaching	Nil	35 (100%)	Disagreed
2	NDU library school have computer Hardware for teaching	Nil	35 (100%)	Disagreed
3	NDU library school have library software for teaching	Nil	35 (100%)	Disagreed
4	NDU library school have audio-visual equipment for teaching	Nil	35 (100%)	Disagreed
5	NDU library school have cataloguing and classification tools for teaching	Nil	35 (100%)	Disagreed

Source: Field survey, 2024.

The table above revealed that all the respondents 35 (100%) disagreed with the statements that NDU library school have electronic library for teaching; NDU library school have computer Hardware for teaching; NDU library school have library software for teaching; NDU library school have audio-visual equipment for teaching; and NDU library school have cataloguing and classification tools for teaching. This implies that in the training and education of LIS students in

NDU, the theoretical aspect of the teaching and learning process is concentrated more on than the practical aspect. The research has found out that, that demonstration library

and laboratory is not available in the Niger Delta University library school.

Research Question Two: What are the challenges that hinder the training and education of library and information science students in the Niger Delta University library school?

Table 5: challenges to training and education of library and information science students

S/n	Statement	Yes (%)	No (%)	Decision
1	Lacking information sources and other facilities for teaching and learning	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
2	Limitations on how to supply library services & enhance teaching and learning using new digital technologies	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
3	Inadequate teaching and learning facilities	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
4	Inadequate industrial attachments	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
5	Shortage of high-ranking teaching staff in Library and Information Science Department	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
6	Skills and attitudes of some LIS lecturers	24 (68.6%)	11 (31.4%)	Agreed
7	Poor information environment	29 (82.9%)	6 (17.1%)	Agreed

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 5 show that Lacking information sources and other facilities for teaching and learning 35 (100%); Limitations on how to supply library services & enhance teaching and learning using new digital technologies 35 (100%); Inadequate teaching and learning facilities 35 (100%); Inadequate industrial attachments 35 (100%); Shortage of high ranking teaching staff in Library and Information Science Department 35 (100%); Skills and attitudes of some LIS lecturers 24 (68.6%); and Poor information environment 29 (82.9%), were agreed to by the respondents as the challenges hindering the smooth training and education of LIS students in NDU.

Research Question Three: What are the likely solutions to the challenges facing training and education of library and information science students in NDU?

Table 6: Probable solutions to the challenges facing library and information science education in NDU

S/n	Statement	Yes (%)	No (%)	Decision
1	The library school curriculum should be revised to emphasize practical aspects of ICT as well as entrepreneurship courses	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
2	The library school lecturers should be adequately and frequently retrained in ICT for teaching and learning	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
3	There should be collaboration among library school to enhance teaching and learning.	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
4	Students should be taken on study visits to standard libraries and ICT centres regularly	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed

5	Proper funding by the authorities to enable the school to acquire relevant ICT material	35 (100%)	nil	Agreed
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Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 6 explained that, The library school curriculum should be revised to emphasize practical aspects of ICT as well as entrepreneurship courses 35 (100%); The library school lecturers should be adequately and frequently retrained in ICT for teaching and learning 35 (100%); There should be collaboration among library school to enhance teaching and learning 35 (100%); Students should be taken on study visits to standard libraries and ICT centres regularly 35 (100%); and Proper funding by the authorities to enable the school to acquire relevant ICT material 35 (100%), were all agreed with as the probable solutions to the challenges identified as hindering the training and education of LIS students in the NDU.

Summary of Findings

This research was conducted to assess the Challenges in the Training and Education of Library and Information Science Students in Nigeria: A Case Study of Niger Delta University. Summary of the major research findings are as follows:

1. The research as found out that, that demonstration library and laboratory are not available in the Niger Delta University library school.
2. Lacking information sources and other facilities for teaching and learning; Limitations on how to supply library services & enhance teaching and learning using new digital technologies; Inadequate teaching and learning facilities; Inadequate industrial attachments; Shortage of high ranking teaching staff in Library and Information Science Department; Skills and attitudes of some LIS lecturers; and Poor information environment, were agreed to by the respondents as the challenges hindering the smooth training and education of LIS students in NDU.
3. The library school curriculum should be revised to emphasize practical aspects of ICT as well as entrepreneurship courses; The library school lecturers should be adequately and

frequently retrained in ICT for teaching and learning; There should be collaboration among library school to enhance teaching and learning; Students should be taken on study visits to standard libraries and ICT centres regularly; and Proper funding by the authorities to enable the school to acquire relevant ICT material, were all agreed with as the probable solutions to the challenges identified as hindering the training and education of LIS students in the NDU.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of research question one (RQ1) revealed that all the respondents 35 (100%) disagreed with the statements that NDU library school have electronic library for teaching; NDU library school have computer Hardware for teaching; NDU library school have library software for teaching; NDU library school have audio-visual equipment for teaching; and NDU library school have cataloguing and classification tools for teaching. This implies that in the training and education of LIS students in NDU, the theoretical aspect of the teaching and learning process is concentrated more on than the practical aspect. The research as found out that, that demonstration library and laboratory are not available in the Niger Delta University library school. This finding is in consonance with Asogwa (2023) who cited Chifwepa (2006) who wrote that most library schools face the problem of facilities shortage leading to inadequate access by students. This inadequacy of facilities in many Nigerian library schools has led to library and information science students being taught largely theoretically (Minishi-Manjanja and Ocholla, 2006). This practice compromises the standard level of competence among the graduates who have received such education and training (Ugwuoke, 2011)

Research question two (RQ2) show that Lacking information sources and other facilities for teaching and learning 35 (100%); Limitations on

how to supply library services & enhance teaching and learning using new digital technologies 35 (100%); Inadequate teaching and learning facilities 35 (100%); Inadequate industrial attachments 35 (100%); Shortage of high ranking teaching staff in Library and Information Science Department 35 (100%); Skills and attitudes of some LIS lecturers 24 (68.6%); and Poor information environment 29 (82.9%), were agreed to by the respondents as the challenges hindering the smooth training and education of LIS students in NDU. This finding is in line with Zakari (2000) which noted that, Lack of ICT (Information Communication Technology) infrastructure constitutes one of the major challenges that ensuring that large number of students acquires ICT skills requires that students have access to appropriate hardware's and software's. This often involves installing and maintaining many classroom workstations or networked computers. This finding is also in support of Asogwa (2023) which averred that, a peep into the library and information science schools show that a good number of them do not have dedicated ICT laboratories as in the case of university of Nigeria Nsukka, Delta State University and so on. In schools where they are available they are inadequate in terms of space and ICT facilities (Jenson, 2005). In continuation, inadequate funding is equally a challenge facing library schools in Nigeria as Manjanja (2006) noted that library schools in Nigeria are constrained by poor funding for as long as funding does not improve appreciably, the present unsatisfied situation in the library schools are unlikely to change for better.

Research question three (RQ3) explained that, The library school curriculum should be revised to emphasize practical aspects of ICT as well as entrepreneurship courses 35 (100%); The library school lecturers should be adequately and frequently retrained in ICT for teaching and learning 35 (100%); There should be collaboration among library school to enhance teaching and learning 35 (100%); Students should be taken on study visits to standard libraries and ICT centres regularly 35 (100%); and Proper funding by the authorities to enable the school to acquire relevant ICT material 35 (100%), were all agreed with as the probable solutions to the

challenges identified as hindering the training and education of LIS students in the NDU. This finding is in tandem with Yemi-Peters & Oladokun (2023) who cited Ejechi (2020) who suggested that Librarians' Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) should take into account a nationwide evaluation of the curricula used in library schools in Nigeria. They added that the curriculum used in library schools needs to be revised in order to take into account contemporary development and technological improvement. Additionally, this study is in line with the findings of Issa et al. (2014) cited by Yemi-Peters & Oladokun (2023) who established that the quality of librarianship has always hinged on contemporary technology. Librarianship, like other professions, has never been the same again due to the growing use of modern technology for information management. Without a question, modern librarianship is significantly reliant on ICT to function in the face of the information explosion. Thus, training and education of library staff members should be planned and updated to reflect trends in technological innovation in order to keep up with the worldwide trend in the profession and to improve job performance.

Conclusion

This study shows that the curriculum for teaching the library and information should be reviewed, more course that will help the student in achieving efficiency and effectiveness on their academic performances, and prepare them for future task should be introduced. The study shows that there is no much interaction between the students and information centers to enhance better knowledge and practical skills. The study also shows that the students should be introduced to practical works and strengthens field works and internship among the student.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were:

1. Review of existing curriculum. It is recommended that there is a need to reorient Library and information Science Education to reflect global changes and evolving market demands.

1. Establishing links and collaborations between Library and Information Science schools and information centres
2. There is a need to introduce and maintain interaction and collaboration between Library and Information Science employers and Library and Information Science professionals particularly the educators to create dialogue among stakeholders.
3. Introduction and strengthening of students field work and internship. Fieldwork training should be introduced for Library and Information Science students so as to impart practical experience and give them opportunity to practice what they learn in classes.
4. More training on Online Resources. By teaching the student of library and information science about online resources and giving an up-to-date information. .

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